

On Inverse Paired Domination in Some Graphs

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Abstract— The set of edges with no common end vertex is called a matching. A matching is perfect if every vertex of the graph is incident to an edge of the matching. The subset of vertex set is a paired dominating set if it is dominating and subgraph induced by it contains a perfect matching. The paired dominating set of minimum cardinality is called minimum paired dominating set. The paired domination number γ_{pr} is the cardinality of a minimum paired dominating set for a graph. Let a subset D of the vertex set $V(G)$ be the minimum paired dominating set for the graph G and if the set $V(G) - D$ contains a paired dominating set D' of the graph G , then D' is an inverse paired dominating set with respect to D . The inverse paired domination number $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of an inverse paired dominating set. In this paper we investigate the inverse paired domination number of power graphs and total graphs of path and cycle.

Keywords— Dominating set, Paired dominating sets, Inverse paired dominating sets, Power graphs, Total graphs.

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I. INTRODUCTION

We begin with simple, finite, connected and undirected graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ without pendant vertex and with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The concept of dominating set is well studied by Berge [1] in 1958 and Ore [9] in 1962. They introduced the terms dominating set and domination number of a graph.

A systematic survey on dominating sets and related concepts can be found in Haynes *et. al.* [3]. The discussion on some advanced topics on the theory of domination is carried out by the same authors in [4]. The concept of inverse domination was introduced by Kulli and Sigarkanti [7] while in [8] Kulli and Nandargi have explored the concept of inverse domination and introduced various inverse dominating sets such as inverse independent dominating set, inverse paired dominating set and inverse induced paired dominating set. The present paper is aimed to report some results investigations in the context of inverse paired dominating sets in graph. For any undefined term in graph theory we refer to Clark and Holtan [2].

II. PRELIMINERIES

Definition 2.1. *The set of edges with no common end vertex is called a matching. A matching is perfect if every vertex of the graph is incident to some edge of the matching.*

Definition 2.2. *The subset D of a vertex set $V(G)$ of a graph G is a paired dominating set if it is a dominating set and subgraph induced by it contains a perfect matching. The paired domination number γ_{pr} is the minimum cardinality of a paired dominating set D for a graph G and D is known as minimum paired dominating set.*

Definition 2.3. Let D be the minimum paired dominating set for a graph G . If $V(G) - D$ contains a paired dominating set D' of G , then D' is called an inverse paired dominating set with respect to D . The inverse paired domination number, denoted by $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(G)$ of G , is the minimum cardinality of an inverse paired dominating set of G .

Definition 2.4. The distance between two vertices u and v is the number of edges in a shortest path connecting them, denoted by $d(u, v)$. The k^{th} power of a graph G , denoted by G^k , is a graph with same vertex set as of G and two vertices u, v are adjacent if the distance between them is at most k .

Definition 2.5. The total graph of a graph $T(G)$ of G , is the graph with the vertex set $V(G) \cup E(G)$ and two vertices are adjacent whenever they are either adjacent or incident in G .

Paired domination number for k^{th} power of path and cycle have been investigated by Isaac and Pandya in [5] and also studied paired domination of degree splitting graph of path and cycle. Further paired domination number of some path and cycle related graphs are investigated in [6] by the same authors.

We state the following existing results for our ready reference.

Observations 2.6. [3]

$$\gamma_{pr}(P_n) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil.$$

$$\gamma_{pr}(C_n) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil.$$

$$\gamma_{pr}(W_n) = 2.$$

$$\gamma_{pr}(K_{m,n}) = 2.$$

Theorem 2.7. [5] $\gamma_{pr}(P_n^k) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rceil$.

Theorem 2.8. [5] $\gamma_{pr}(C_n^k) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rceil$.

Theorem 2.9. [6] $\gamma_{pr}(T(P_n)) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n-1}{3} \right\rceil$.

Theorem 2.10. [6] $\gamma_{pr}(T(C_n)) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$.

III. INVERSE PAIRED DOMINATION OF SOME STANDARD GRAPHS

Theorem 3.1. For $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(C_n) = \frac{n}{2}$.

Proof. Let C_n be the cycle with n vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n$ such that $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. Then $D = \{v_1, v_2, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}\}$ is a minimum paired dominating set for $V(C_n)$.

Consider $D' = \{v_{i+2} : v_i \in D\}$. Then D' is also a paired dominating set and $D' \subset V(C_n) - D$. Hence D' is an inverse paired dominating set for $V(C_n)$ and therefore, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(C_n) = \frac{n}{2}$. ■

Remark 3.2: In the case when $n \equiv 1, 2, 3 \pmod{4}$, $\gamma_{pr}(C_n) > \frac{n}{2}$ and if D is minimum paired dominating

set, $|V(C_n) - D| < \frac{n}{2}$ and hence it is not possible to find paired dominating set from $V(C_n) - D$. Therefore inverse paired domination number does not exist for $n \equiv 1,2,3(mod 4)$.

For the better explanation consider the case of C_{14} . Here $n = 14 \equiv 2(mod 4)$. In Figure 1, the solid vertices represents a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. By observation we can say, it is not possible to find a paired dominating set from the set of remaining vertices which meets the requirement to be a paired dominating set of C_{14} .

Figure 1: Paired dominating set in C_{14}

Figure 2: Paired and inverse paired dominating set in C_{12}

Illustration 3.3: Consider the cycle C_{12} , it is the case where $n \equiv 0(mod 4)$. As shown in Figure 2 the set of solid vertices $\{v_1, v_2, v_5, v_6, v_9, v_{10}\}$ represents the paired dominating set while the set of hollow vertices $\{v_3, v_4, v_7, v_8, v_{11}, v_{12}\}$ represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence $\gamma_{pr}(C_{12}) = 4$.

Theorem 3.4. For wheel graph $W_n = C_n + 1$, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(W_n) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{4} \rfloor$.

Proof. Let W_n be the wheel with $n + 1$ vertices $w, v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n$ where w is an apex vertex and v_i 's are rim vertices. Consider $D = \{w, v_1\}$. Then it is a minimum paired dominating set.

For $n \equiv 0(mod 4)$, $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7, \dots, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}\} \subseteq V(C_n) - D$ is an inverse paired dominating set of minimum cardinality. Therefore, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(W_n) = \frac{2n}{4}$.

For $n \equiv 1(mod 4)$, $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7, \dots, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(C_n) - D$ and for $n \equiv 2(mod 4)$, $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7, \dots, v_{n-4}, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}\} \subseteq V(C_n) - D$ are inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality $2 \lfloor \frac{n}{4} \rfloor$. Therefore, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(W_n) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{4} \rfloor$. ■

Illustration 3.5 Consider the wheel graph W_8 . As shown in Figure 3, the solid vertices $\{v, v_1\}$ represents the paired dominating set while in the Figure 4, the solid vertices $\{v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7\}$ represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(W_8) = 4$.

Figure 3: Paired dominating set in W_8

Figure 4: Inverse paired dominating set in W_8

Theorem 3.6. For $m, n > 1$, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(K_{m,n}) = 2$.

Proof. Let $K_{m,n}$ be the bipartite graph with partition $V(K_{m,n}) = U \cup V$ where $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n\}$ and $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_m\}$. Consider $D = \{u_1, v_1\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set.

Let $D' = \{v_2, u_2\} \subseteq V(K_{m,n}) - D$. Then D' is a minimum paired dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(K_{m,n}) = 2$. ■

Illustration 3.7: Figure 5 and Figure 6 represent complete bipartite graph $K_{3,4}$. As shown in Figure 5, the solid vertices $\{u_1, v_1\}$ represents the minimum paired dominating set while in Figure 6, the solid vertices $\{u_2, v_2\}$ represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(K_{3,4}) = 2$.

Figure 5: Paired dominating set in $K_{3,4}$

Figure 6: Inverse paired dominating set in $K_{3,4}$

IV. INVERSE PAIRED DOMINATION IN POWER GRAPHS OF PATH AND CYCLE

We recall the Definition 2.4 and prove the following results.

Theorem 4.1. For $k > 1, n \geq 4$ and $k < n - 1, \gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = \begin{cases} 2 + \frac{2n}{3k+1} & \text{for } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3k+1} \\ 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \rfloor & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Proof. Let P_n be the path with n vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n$. Then $V(P_n^k) = V(P_n)$ and $E(P_n^k) = \{v_i v_j; d(v_i, v_j) \leq k \text{ in } G\}$. Note that, for $k \geq n - 1$, the graph P_n^k will be complete graph and the inverse paired domination number is 2. Hence we consider the following cases.

Case 1: $n = 4$.

For $n = 4, k = 2$ and P_4^2 is shown in the Figure 7.

Figure 7: Paired and inverse paired domination in P_4^2

Consider $D = \{v_1, v_2\}$. Then it is minimal paired dominating set. Consider $D' = \{v_3, v_4\}$. It is also a paired

dominating set such that $D \cap D' = \phi$. Hence $\gamma_{pr}(P_4^2) = \gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_4^2) = 2$.

Case 2: $k < n < 2k + 1, n \neq 4$.

We begin with $D = \{v_1, v_k\} \subseteq V(P_n^k)$ with $d(v_1, v_k) = k - 1 \leq k$ in P_n , implies $v_1 v_k \in E(P_n^k)$ where the vertex v_1 dominates the vertices $v_2, v_3, v_4, \dots, v_k$ while the vertex v_k dominates the vertices $v_1, v_{k+1}, v_{k+2}, \dots, v_n$. Hence D is a paired dominating set and it is with minimum cardinality as $|D| = 2$.

Let $D' = \{v_2, v_{k+1}\} \subseteq V(P_n^k) - D$ with $d(v_2, v_{k+1}) = k - 1 \leq k$ in P_n , implies $v_2 v_{k+1} \in E(P_n^k)$ where the vertex v_2 dominates the vertices $v_1, v_3, v_4, \dots, v_{k+1}$ while the vertex v_{k+1} dominates the vertices $v_2, v_{k+2}, v_{k+3}, \dots, v_n$. Hence D' is a paired dominating set and it is with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = 2$.

Therefore, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2$ for $k < n < 2k + 1, n \neq 4$.

Case 3: $2k < n < 3k + 1$.

Consider the sets $D = \{v_k, v_{2k}\}$ and $D' = \{v_{k+1}, v_{2k+1}\}$. Then the sets are disjoint minimum paired dominating sets. Therefore D' is an inverse paired dominating set.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2$ for $2k < n < 3k + 1$.

Case 4: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3k + 1}$.

Consider the minimum paired dominating set $D = \{v_{k+1}, v_{2k+1}, v_{4k+2}, v_{5k+2}, \dots, v_{n-2k}, v_{n-k}\}$ with cardinality $|D| = \frac{2n}{3k+1}$.

Let a function $f: V(P_n^k) \rightarrow V(P_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i+1}$ and $f(v_n) = v_1$.

It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $S = f(D)$. Then the set S dominates the set $V(P_n^k)$ pairwise except the vertex v_1 . To dominate the whole set pairwise, we have to add a pair of vertices. Let $D' = \{v_1, v_2\} \cup S$. Then the set D' is a paired dominating set and $D \cap D' = \phi$. Therefore, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2 + \frac{2n}{3k+1}$ for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3k + 1}$.

Case 5: $n \equiv a \pmod{3k + 1}$ where $a < k$.

Consider $n = t(3k + 1) + a$. Let $D = \{v_{k+1}, v_{2k+1}, v_{4k+2}, v_{5k+2}, \dots, v_{t(3k+1)-2k}, v_{t(3k+1)-k}, v_{n-1}, v_n\}$.

Then $|D| = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rceil$.

Let a function $f: V(P_n^k) \rightarrow V(P_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i+a}$, $f(v_{n-1}) = v_1$ and $f(v_n) = v_2$. It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $D' = f(D)$. Then the set D' is a paired dominating set for the set $V(P_n^k)$ and it is of minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D|$. And as $D \cap D' = \phi$, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2 \left\lceil \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rceil$ for $n \equiv a \pmod{3k + 1}$ where $a < k$.

Case 6: $n \equiv k \pmod{3k + 1}$ for $k = 2$.

Consider $n = t(3(2) + 1) + 2 = 7t + 2$.

Let $D = \{v_3, v_5, v_{10}, v_{12}, \dots, v_{7t-4}, v_{7t-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n\}$. Then $|D| = \left\lceil \frac{2n}{7} \right\rceil$. Let a function $f: V(P_n^k) \rightarrow V(P_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i+3}$, $f(v_{7t-2}) = v_{7t}$, $f(v_{n-1}) = v_1$ and $f(v_n) = v_2$. It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $D' = f(D)$. Then the set D' is a paired dominating set for the set $V(P_n^k)$ and it is of minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D|$. And as $D \cap D' = \phi$, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{7} \right\rceil$ for $n \equiv a \pmod{3k + 1}; k = 2$.

Case 7: $n \equiv k \pmod{3k + 1}$ for $k > 2$.

Consider $n = t(3k + 1) + k$.

Let $D = \{v_k, v_{2k}, v_{4k+1}, v_{5k+1}, \dots, v_{t(3k+1)-(2k+1)}, v_{t(3k+1)-(k+1)}, v_{n-1}, v_n\}$. Then $|D| = 2 \left\lceil \frac{2n}{3k+1} \right\rceil$.

Let a function $f: V(P_n^k) \rightarrow V(P_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i+k+1}$, $f(v_{n-1}) = v_1$ and $f(v_n) = v_2$. It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $D' = f(D)$. Then the set D' is a paired dominating set for the set $V(P_n^k)$ and it is of minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D|$. And as $D \cap D' = \phi$, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rfloor$ for $n \equiv a \pmod{3k+1}$ for $k > 2$.

Case 8: $n \equiv a \pmod{3k+1}$; $k < a \leq 2k+1$.

Consider $n = t(3k+1) + a$.

Let $D = \{v_{k+1}, v_{2k+1}, v_{4k+2}, v_{5k+2}, \dots, v_{t(3k+1)-2k}, v_{t(3k+1)-k}, v_{t(3k+1)+(k-1)}, v_{t(3k+1)+(k+1)}\}$.

Then $|D| = 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rfloor$. Let a function $f: V(P_n^k) \rightarrow V(P_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i-1}$ and $f(v_1) = v_n$. It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $D' = f(D)$. Then the set D' is a paired dominating set for the set $V(P_n^k)$ and it is of minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D|$. And as $D \cap D' = \phi$, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rfloor$ for $n \equiv a \pmod{3k+1}$; $k < a < 2k+1$.

Case 9: $n \equiv a \pmod{3k+1}$; $2k+1 < a < 3k+1$.

Consider $n = t(3k+1) + a$.

Let $D = \{v_{k+1}, v_{2k+1}, v_{4k+2}, v_{5k+2}, \dots, v_{t(3k+1)-2k}, v_{t(3k+1)-k}, v_{t(3k+1)+(k+1)}, v_{t(3k+1)+(2k+1)}\}$.

Then $|D| = 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rfloor$. Let a function $f: V(P_n^k) \rightarrow V(P_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i-1}$ and $f(v_1) = v_n$. It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $D' = f(D)$. Then the set D' is a paired dominating set for the set $V(P_n^k)$ and it is minimum as $|D'| = |D|$. And as $D \cap D' = \phi$, D' is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rfloor$ for $n \equiv a \pmod{3k+1}$; $2k+1 < a < 3k+1$.

Thus in all the cases discussed above we have, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(P_n^k) = \begin{cases} 2 + \frac{2n}{3k+1} & \text{for } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3k+1}. \\ 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \right\rfloor & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Illustration 4.2. Consider the path P_{10} and $k = 3$. It is the case related to case 3 of Theorem 4.1. Figure 8 and Figure 9 represent the power graph P_{10}^3 . As shown in the Figure 8, set of solid vertices $\{v_4, v_8\}$ represents a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality while the set of solid vertices $\{v_5, v_9\}$ in Figure 9 represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence $\gamma_{pr}(P_{10}^3) = 2$. ■

Figure 8: Paired dominating set in P_{10}^3

Figure 9: Inverse paired dominating set in P_{10}^3

Theorem 4.3. For $k > 1, n \geq 4$ and $k < \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor, \gamma_{pr}^{-1}(C_n^k) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \rfloor$.

Proof. Let C_n be the cycle with n vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n$. Then $V(C_n^k) = V(C_n)$ and $E(C_n^k) = \{v_i v_j : d(v_i, v_j) \leq k \text{ in } G\}$. We note that, the graph C_n^k is $2k$ regular graph and hence for $k \geq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ the graph C_n^k is a complete graph K_n and $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(K_n) = 2$ which is very obvious. Therefore we consider only the case for which $k < \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$.

Let $n \equiv 0(mod 3k + 1)$.

Consider the minimum paired dominating set $D = \{v_1, v_{k+1}, v_{3k+2}, v_{4k+2}, \dots, v_{n-3k}, v_{n-2k}\}$.

Then $|D| = \frac{2n}{3k+1}$. Let a function $f: V(C_n^k) \rightarrow V(C_n^k)$ defined as $f(v_i) = v_{i+1}$ and $f(v_n) = v_1$.

It can be easily verified that f is one-one and onto. Consider the set $D' = f(D)$. Then the set D' is also a paired dominating set as the graph is regular. The set D' is a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = \frac{2n}{3k+1}$. And as $D \cap D' = \emptyset, D'$ is an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality.

Hence $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(C_n^k) = \frac{2n}{3k+1}$ for $n \equiv 0(mod 3k + 1)$.

For other cases the proof is similar to theorem 3.1.

And hence For $k > 1, n \geq 4$ and $k < \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor, \gamma_{pr}^{-1}(C_n^k) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3k+1} \rfloor$. ■

Illustration 4.4. Consider the cycle C_{14} with $k = 2$. Figure 10 and Figure 11 represent the power graph C_{14}^2 . The set of solid vertices $\{v_1, v_3, v_8, v_{10}\}$ shown in Figure 10 represents a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality while the set of solid vertices $\{v_2, v_4, v_9, v_{11}\}$ shown in Figure 11 represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence $\gamma_{pr}(C_{14}^2) = 4$.

Figure 10: Paired dominating set in C_{14}^2

Figure 11: Inverse paired dominating set in C_{14}^2

V. INVERSE PAIRED DOMINATION IN TOTAL GRAPH OF PATH AND CYCLE

We recall the Definition 2.5 and prove the following results.

Theorem 5.1. For $n > 2$, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(P_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Proof. Let $V(P_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the vertex set and $E(P_n) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{n-1}\}$ be the edge set of P_n . By the definition of total graph, $V(T(P_n)) = V(P_n) \cup E(P_n)$. Consider the following cases to prove the result.

Case 1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

Consider the set $D = \{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, \dots, e_{n-2}, e_{n-1}\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set with cardinality $\frac{2n}{3}$. Consider $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(T(P_n)) - D$. It is also a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D| = \frac{2n}{3}$. Thus $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(P_n)) = \frac{2n}{3}$.

Case 2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Consider the set $D = \{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, \dots, e_{n-4}, e_{n-3}, e_{n-2}, e_{n-1}\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set with cardinality $2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$. Consider $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(T(P_n)) - D$. It is also a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D| = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Thus $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(P_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Case 3: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

Consider the set $D = \{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, \dots, e_{n-4}, e_{n-3}, e_{n-2}, e_{n-1}\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set with cardinality $2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$. Consider $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(T(P_n)) - D$. It is also a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D| = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Thus $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(P_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Hence in all the cases described above we have, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(P_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$. ■

Illustration 5.2: Consider the total graph of path P_8 as shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13. $T(P_8)$ shows illustration of case 3 of above theorem. As shown in Figure 12 set of solid vertices $\{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, e_6, e_7\}$ represents a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality while in Figure 13 the set of solid vertices $\{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8\}$ represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence $\gamma_{pr}(T(P_8)) = 6$.

Figure 12: Paired dominating set in $T(P_8)$

Figure 13: Inverse paired dominating set in $T(P_8)$

Theorem 5.3. For $n > 2$, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(C_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Proof. Let $V(C_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the vertex set and $E(C_n) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{n-1}, e_n\}$ be the edge set of C_n . By the definition of total graph, $V(T(C_n)) = V(C_n) \cup E(C_n)$.

Case 1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

Consider the set $D = \{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, \dots, e_{n-2}, e_{n-1}\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set with cardinality $\frac{2n}{3}$. Consider $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(T(C_n)) - D$. It is also a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = \frac{2n}{3}$. Thus $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(C_n)) = \frac{2n}{3}$.

Case 2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Consider the set $D = \{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, \dots, e_{n-4}, e_{n-3}, e_{n-2}, e_{n-1}\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set with cardinality $2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$. Consider $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(T(C_n)) - D$. It is also a paired dominating set and with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D| = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Thus $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(C_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Case 3: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

Consider the set $D = \{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, \dots, e_{n-4}, e_{n-3}, e_{n-2}, e_{n-1}\}$. Then D is a minimum paired dominating set with cardinality $2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$. Consider $D' = \{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, \dots, v_{n-3}, v_{n-2}, v_{n-1}, v_n\} \subseteq V(T(C_n)) - D$. It is also a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality as $|D'| = |D| = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Thus $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(C_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$.

Hence in all the cases described above we have, $\gamma_{pr}^{-1}(T(C_n)) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{3} \rfloor$. ■

Illustration 5.4: Consider the total graph of cycle C_9 as shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15. $T(C_9)$ shows illustration of case 1 of above theorem. As shown in Figure 14 the set of solid vertices $\{e_1, e_2, e_4, e_5, e_7, e_8\}$ represents a paired dominating set with minimum cardinality while in Figure 15 the set of solid vertices $\{v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6, v_8, v_9\}$ represents an inverse paired dominating set with minimum cardinality. Hence $\gamma_{pr}(T(P_8)) = 6$.

Figure 15: Inverse paired dominating set in $T(C_9)$

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The concept of paired domination and inverse paired domination helps to strengthen the security and reduce vulnerability of any network. Here we have investigated inverse paired domination number of the larger graphs obtained from path and cycle by means of some graph operations.

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